

The Contribution Of Socio-Emotional Support To Arab Adolescents With Reading Disabilities

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Abstract

The study aims to examine the contribution of socio-emotional support among Arab adolescents with reading disabilities. It also focuses on socio-emotional support as a mediating variable that has an impact on self-image, social competence, reading disability and academic achievement. Indeed, the study examines how reading disability is influenced by the Arab culture that is an integral part of the upbringing for Arab adolescents of various ages, including early adolescence (junior high school) and late adolescence (high school). The study population is composed of 381 Arab adolescents: 115 males with reading disabilities and 60 males with normal reading ability, as well as 91 females with reading disabilities and 115 females with normal reading ability. The researchers used three questionnaires that the study population responded to: Social Competence Questionnaire, Self-Image Questionnaire and Socio-Emotional Support Questionnaire. In addition, the study was reviewed via two tests: Reading Accuracy Test and Reading Comprehension Test. The findings showed that the level of social competence among Arab adolescent males and females with reading disability is lower than that of normal Arab adolescent males and females. Indeed, the study indicates that there is a positive correlation between socio-emotional support indicators and academic achievements among adolescent students with reading disabilities. In addition, students with reading disabilities who received emotional support, report lower emotional and social indicators, as well as lower academic achievements than normal students.

Introduction

Adolescence is often associated with stress and distress, and increases the significance of socio-emotional support, as well as the importance of the need to receive help from the environment. (Lewis, Amatya, Coffman & Ollendick, 2015). Researchers in the field of learning disabilities agree (NJCLD, 2011) that in order to understand them, it would be appropriate to examine the way students function in different learning environments and in different stages of development, while addressing diverse cultures and environments, as well as personal and emotional resources. (AL-Yagon & Margalit, 2013). Interaction between difficulties and resources determine the intensity of disabilities in daily life. In this situation, intervention, social emotional support, and good quality teaching are of major significance, providing a solution to the learning difficulties with high chances to adapt and succeed in life, both from social and personal-emotional perspective (Han, 2014).

Due to the disability, the child finds it difficult to select effective patterns for solving problems, and the frustration may be expressed by avoidance, resistance, passive sadness and anger attacks (Agbaria & Daher, 2015.) The child develops defensive patterns and his/her self-image is damaged. Due to the difficulties that characterize children with learning disabilities, they might deviate from their path, and the behavioral, emotional and social problems will worsen. Therefore, the concept of treating students with learning disabilities that is currently being established, suggests that the treatment should be integrated and multidisciplinary. A complete therapeutic program should include socio-emotional support, while treating the child as an individual and the family as a system, in addition to the cultural, educational and socio-emotional environment.

The Arab culture with its conservative, traditional and collectivist nature refers to a child with learning disabilities as to someone who has an inferior status and perceived negatively, which adversely affects the child's cognitive, emotional and social development that is not compatible with his peers (Tarabia & Abu-Rabia, 2016). Moreover, Arab culture refers to children with learning disabilities in general and reading disabilities in particular as irregular students who do not belong and are a source of shame for the family. This negative reference adversely affects the self-image and social competence, eventually leading to insufficient academic achievements.

This study aims to shed light on the socio-emotional support among adolescent students with reading disabilities in Arab culture, and will allow us to understand the extent of its contribution to the adolescent in his/her opinion.

This study will also review the emotional support, whether at home or at school, and its contribution to socio-emotional variables (social competence and self-image) and accomplishments of adolescents who do or do not have reading disabilities. In other words, socio-emotional support is a mediating variable that affects self-image, social competence, reading disability and academic achievements among Arab adolescents of different ages: early adolescence, i.e. junior high school, and late adolescence – high school years. Hence and in line with what has been mentioned above, there is likely to be a link between social emotional support and social competence, image and academic achievement. To examine the subject of the study, several hypotheses were established: **a.** Adolescents with reading disabilities will report a lower level of social competence, self-image and academic achievements compared to a group of normal adolescents. **b.** There is a positive correlation between socio-emotional support indicators and academic achievements among adolescent students with reading disabilities. **c.** Students with reading disabilities who received emotional support would still report lower emotional and social indicators, as well as lower academic achievements than normal students.

Therefore, the questions at the heart of this study are: What are the social characteristics (social competence) and the emotional characteristics (self-image) of Arab students' males and females with reading disabilities in adolescence (in early and late adolescence)? What are the differences between Arab students with reading disabilities who received socio-emotional support and those who did not? To which extent does socio-emotional support have an impact on reading disability and socio-emotional characteristics among all adolescents reviewed?

Literature Review

Definition of reading disability

This study has been prompted by the significant increase in the prevalence of learning disabilities over the past 20 years (Goldstein 2011; Spector, 2005). In 1976, about 2% of students were reported to have this disorder; in 1990, approximately 5%, and in recent years, the reported frequency of learning disabilities in literature-oriented and educational institutions amounts to 10%-15% of the population. Since the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) was enacted in 1990, the percentage of those who report to have been diagnosed with learning disability is increasing each year.

In Israel, the current reports indicate that the prevalence of students with learning disabilities increases at a faster rate than the international average. A report by the Central Bureau of Statistics (2010) revealed that in the 2006-2007 school year, about one-fifth (19.9%) of 10-12 grade students, including the Arab education system, were granted an adjustment for reading the matriculation exams. The findings in Israel indicate a higher incidence in boys (61.5%) than in girls (38.5%) (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2009), and an increase in the assessment of the prevalence of students with the increase in age. The main increase in the frequency of students with learning disabilities occurs in high school (Amiram & Racheli, 2014).

The National Joint Committee on Learning Disabilities (NJCLD) has expanded and updated the 1994 definition of dyslexia, which states that dyslexia is a specific learning disability that is neurobiological in origin. It is characterized by difficulties with accurate and/or fluent word recognition and by poor spelling and decoding abilities. These difficulties typically result from a deficit in the phonological component of the language that is often unexpected in relation to other cognitive abilities and the provision of effective classroom instruction. Secondary implications may include problems with reading comprehension and reduced reading experience that can impede growth of vocabulary and background knowledge (Frost, 2005, 2012).

It should be noted that in 2011, after receiving updated research results, the National Joint Committee members emphasized the scientific basis for the existence of neurobiological and neurological processes leading to learning disabilities and low academic achievements. They noted that learning disabilities appear in different groups of students belonging to various cultures: disabilities appear in different races among populations belonging to diverse socioeconomic statuses, in boys and in girls. Therefore, it is considered an up-to-date definition, which presents a dynamic multi-dimensional ecological model (NJCLD, 2011).

In Israel, dyslexia is defined as "reading disability that stems from neuropsychological disruptions that impairs the ability to achieve meaningful reading." (Director General Circular, 1992). There are many factors for this phenomenon. It is characterized by an inability to read at the expected level according to age, intelligence and grade, and by an existence of a two-year gap at the least between the chronological age and the reading age (Spector, 2005; Goldstein, 2011). Impairments in the ability to learn how to read fluently and accurately or obtain information and meaning from a written material, can stem from language problems, deficit in decoding the script which is expressed in deletions and/or additions of sounds, or distortions and exchange of sounds or parts of words (Director General Circular, 1996).

Alongside the difficulties in the academic field described above, studies indicate that students with reading disability experience socio-emotional difficulties. These students report negative self-perception and low self-esteem primarily in the academic sphere (Burden, 2008; Cobati, 2015; Glazzard, 2010). Moreover, they report more symptoms of general and social anxiety and depression (Mammarella et al., 2014).

Attitude of Arab society towards RDs

The Arab society in Israel is an ethnic, religious, linguistic, cultural and national minority (Smootha, 2010). The Arab population constitutes 20% of the State of Israel and includes about 1.5 million people. This minority comprises a majority of 82% Muslims and a minority of 9% Christians and 9% Druze. The Arabs in Israel are a homogeneous minority group, even though they contain Muslims, Christians and Druze. They speak the same language and follow the same cultural codes (Peleg, 2009; Toma, 2016). It is a conservative society and its values are reflected in its passive approach to life. It is considered a collectivist and patriarchal society (Haj-Yahia, 2003). A collectivist society puts the nuclear and extended family in the center. The individual experiences only little autonomous personal space and acts out of need to avoid negative judgment by the environment in order to preserve dignity and reputation, and keep himself and his family from "shame" (Cobati, 2015).

A number of studies have examined attitudes and perceptions of the Arab society towards children with learning disabilities (Ben-Ari & Lavee, 2004; Zuniga & Fischer, 2010). These studies indicate that the Arab society holds negative attitudes toward people with learning disabilities. It was also found that in multicultural societies, Arabic speakers express a negative attitude toward people with learning disabilities more than those who speak other languages. It should be noted that attitudes are part of the social norms and culture of the individual (Matsumoto, 2000; Sadeh, 2011; Zuniga, & Fischer, 2010).

Crabtree (Crabtree, 2007) reviewed Arab families with children that have special needs and found that they harbor negative attitudes, since most families whose children have learning disabilities are not accepted by society. Such rejection leads to a division in the family and to lack of cooperation among its members in order to bypass the disability. It is usually considered the mother's fault. Azar and Kurdahi Badr (Azar & Kurdahi Badr, 2010) report a similar finding. They claim that despite the tendency of Arab countries to adopt Western norms and values, the sense of shame is deeply rooted when a child with a flaw or disability is born. The mother tries to hide the child and take care of him/her at home, especially when it is a daughter. Similarly, the attitudes towards individuals with learning disabilities in the Arab society in Israel are negative and stigmatic (Ben-Ari & Lavee, 2004). As the current study examines the effect of reading disability on adolescent boys and girls, it is necessary to define the characteristics of adolescence.

Adolescence

Adolescents experience physiological, emotional and socio-familial changes that require them to re-adapt. Since adolescents are not a homogenous group, each adolescent adapts differently at that age (Agbaria & Daher, 2015; Delay, Hafen, Cunha, Weber & Laursen, 2013). Adolescence refers to the stage of "identity versus confusion" in which the adolescent links the sexual needs, as well as emotional behavior wellbeing, to the skills he/she will develop in order to comply with social norms and requirements and transition from childhood to adulthood. The identity develops through dynamic and continuous interaction between the self and the other, driven by desire to feel belonging and establish a positive self and group identity (Idan & Margalit, 2014; Tanos, 2017).

Studies that deal with handling the difficulties found that students with RDs perceive themselves as less capable of coping than their peers (Sima et al., 2016). Adolescents with reading disabilities feel the need to be accepted by significant adult figures in their lives, such as their parents and teachers (Lavoie, 2005).

Social competence

Social competence is the ability of an individual to establish and develop appropriate social relationships with others. It is defined as learned behaviors that affect the individual's relationship with adult peer groups (Han, 2014; Tarabia & Abu-Rabia, 2016); Vaughn, 1985; Zuniga & Fischer, 2010).

Gresham (Gresham, 1988) presents an expanded definition of social skills that are considered significant in the development of social competence. Her definition includes three main areas: (1) Interpersonal behavior patterns: social skills that enable the individual to cooperate with others, both his peers and adults, to accept authority and be attentive to the requests of others. For example, conversational skills that are compatible with the environment and culture they belong to; (2) Patterns of behavior linked to the individual: social skills that allow him/her to express positive or negative feelings toward himself/herself and the environment; (3) Behavioral patterns related to functioning: social skills that allow the individual to listen and follow instructions in an effort to perform them well and as expected socially, to develop an ability to work independently and demonstrate self-control, to initiate tasks focus on them until completion. This expanded definition includes assertiveness, empathy, self-control, initiative and cooperation. These will be the functions examined in this study via a social competence questionnaire divided into these four categories.

Numerous scholars claimed that learning disability is directly associated with social deficits and difficulties among children and adults with RDs (Gresham & Reschly, 1987; Idan & Margalit, 2014; Margalit, 2014; Sima et al., 2016; Tarabia & Abu-Rabia, 2016). According to this approach, disabilities lead directly to deficits and difficulties in social skills, and as a result, to loneliness and isolation, and therefore, they are two sides of the same coin. Consequently, a negative feedback loop is created –RDs experiences loneliness and lack of social interaction, which prevent them from acquiring an acceptable and appropriate social behavior, and so forth (Idan & Margalit, 2014).

Self-image and RDs

Self-image is an evaluation that the individual develops and enhances regarding himself/herself. The individual's self-image develops and changes over the years, and is affected by the attitude of people surrounding the person since childhood, especially during the period of adolescence, which is a significant developmental period (Saada, 2009; Tarabia & Abu-Rabia, 2016). Self-image can be defined as a set of links, some of which are internal, such as the person's identity in his/her own eyes, satisfaction with manner of behavior, as well as external aspects, such as body image and moral, family, and social image (Akinci, 2011; Friedman, 2007).

Various studies indicate that primary socio-cultural factors are part of the adolescents' self-image shaping, which is defined as a representation of an emotional sense of well-being and that, in turn, is related to successful coping with development tasks (Deihl, Vicary & Deike, 1997). Thus, during adolescence, self-image is perceived as both a factor and a result, and is influenced by and affects the individual's responses while facing a variety of situations and experiences. However, in the minority groups, self-image is perceived as an individual assessment of acceptance in the ethnic group and as a measure of social acceptance and emotional experiences.

Studies indicated a link between self-image and academic achievements. Dyslexia as a sub group of RDs was found to be associated with poor self-perception and various emotional difficulties, including anxiety, depression, and behavior problems (Agbaria & Daher, 2015; Undheim, Wichstrom & Sund, 2011), dropping out of school and suicidal tendencies. In light of the above, there is a need to create social conditions (socio-emotional support) containing elements of approval.

Socio-emotional support

Emotional social support is help and protection provided to others (Han, 2014; Shirey, 2004). Such help can be tangible or intangible, while protection involves shielding and protecting others from the negative effects of life pressure. Therefore, inherently to the definition, the basis of social support involves reciprocity, which includes the exchange of resources between two people at the least. Support includes two components: sources and functions (Sarason, Levine, Basham & Sarason, 1983; Sarason, Shearin, Pierce & Sarason, 1987; Zhang et al., 2015). Researchers describe it differently. Some emphasize the structure of social relations as it is expressed in social media, while others emphasize the messages of help and assistance as they are presented by sources of support and received by support recipients. These messages are organized and categorized according to their support functions (Wills, 1985). The main functions are: (a) instrumental support that provides tangible assistance, including economic assistance, resource satisfaction and solutions, and social services that will assist the adolescent to cope; (b) social support that provides a need for society, belonging and possibility to share daily problems and concerns, and is expressed through social contacts; (c) informative support that provides cognitive tools for assessing problem situations, counseling, guidance and advising, and clarifies situations and stressors, and also provides alternative solutions; (d) motivational support that provides empowerment and encouragement, and increases the self-image and self-confidence of the adolescent regarding a specific field, such as academic achievements; (e) emotional support - a function that meets the need for appreciation, love, acceptance and relations that convey caring, confidence and trust (Saada, 2000, 2007).

Providing social and emotional support to adolescent students may have a significant impact on the socio-emotional aspect. The academic achievements of adolescent students are directly related to emotional stress and state. An appropriate explanation for this is that adolescent students are empowered socially and emotionally in conjunction with their academic tasks (Saada, 2007). Students, who perceive themselves as not benefiting from social support, express negative attitudes toward the learning environment and are perceived as having low academic self-image and achievements (Conory & Elliot, 2004; Idan & Margalit, 2014). Adolescents have to pay particular attention to socio-emotional processes. Therefore, the discussion of socio-emotional support in context of reading disabilities will revolve around the question that focuses on the results of such support - does it affect self-image and social competence, and does it improve academic achievements?

Methodology

study population

The study population included 381 students: 206 boys and girls diagnosed as RD. That group comprised of 115 boys and 91 girls divided as follows: 101 junior high school and 105 high school students diagnosed according to the Ministry of Education criteria, as well as didactic and psychological tests. In addition, a group of 175 normal boys and girls comprised of 60 boys and 115 girls, of whom 81 were junior high school students and 94 high schools' students. The normal participants served as a control group that was compared to the experimental group in order to obtain reliable and clear results about the phenomenon and its implications. The study population was diverse and included Arab students from Israel's Northern District and students from middle to high socioeconomic backgrounds. They were divided into two different age groups: a group of adolescents aged 12-15 and studying in junior high school is called "Early Adolescence Group", and the youngsters aged 16-18 studying in high school is called "Late Adolescence Group". All of them belong to the Arab sector and study in Arab schools, as part of both regular and integrated education systems.

Research tools

1. Self-image questionnaire (Alpha = 0.94) - a questionnaire compiled by Glanz (1989) named "He/she is... and I am...". This questionnaire was translated and adapted to Arabic. It includes 38 items.
2. Social competence (Ghesham & Elliott, 1990) (Alpha = 0.90) - a questionnaire aimed to examine social competence. It was originally written in Hebrew and translated into Arabic for the purpose of this study. The questionnaire includes 39 items describing behavior in various social situations that are ranked on a five-point scale: 1 - "Never"; 2 - "Sometimes, to a small extent"; 3. "Sometimes, to a moderate extent"; 4 - "Sometimes, to a large extent"; 5 - "All the time (always)". The score received is the average rating of all the items. The higher the numerical amount obtained, the higher the level of social competence and vice versa. The scores range from 39 to 108 per the entire questionnaire. The questionnaire provides scores in four categories: cooperation, assertiveness, self-control and empathy.

Emotional support:

The emotional support was reviewed via the SSFI + SSQ questionnaire, while social support was measured via the questionnaire reviewing the educational atmosphere at school and within the family, which supports school-related emotional and motivational issues, such as understanding, acceptance and interest, encouragement and empowerment, supervision and discipline, caring and appreciation. In other words, social emotional support is: emotional support + school support in both aspects.

3. **SSFI Questionnaire:** Aimed to review emotional support (Munsch & Blyth, 1993) (Alpha = 0.83). The questionnaire includes six items, e.g. "Upon necessity, the significant people around me make me feel comfortable". The questionnaire will measure the available support and the perception of support as being realized.
4. **SSQ Questionnaire:** Aimed to review social support (supporters and helpers) (Alpha = 0.92) (Seginer, 1992 Sarason et al., 1983). This questionnaire will allow to measure the support system characteristics: support, frequency, sources and availability.
5. **Home studying Questionnaire:** (Seginer, 1991) (Alpha = 0.86). This questionnaire includes two scales representing two aspects of educational atmosphere that supports school related subjects (emotional and motivational). One contains 7 items of educational and emotional support relating to such subjects, as understanding, acceptance and interest. For example: "My parents give me the feeling that even if I do not succeed, they will still love me". The second contains 12 items of educational and motivational support regarding such issues, as encouraging empowerment, supervision and discipline, caring and appreciation. For example: "In our family, we support only those who succeed".
6. **Reading comprehension test** for junior high school students (Alpha = 0.90). The test was conducted under the guidance of a team of Arabic teachers and includes a section in Arabic ("The end of brave lion") taken from a website entitled "Come to learn Arabic" - www.alarabeyya.com. This section suits the examinees' age and includes 13 multiple-choice questions the answers to which can be found in the text. The test was previously launched in a pilot for reliability and validation by a professional reading disability diagnostician and later became a diagnostic tool in the field. There are four answers for each question and the examinees have to choose the correct one. All the answers exist in the text, which is two pages long, punctuated and includes pictures that illustrate the content.
7. Reading comprehension test for high school students (Alpha = 0.86). This is the "Meitzav" test (school efficiency and growth indicators). The "Meitzav" format combines a standard external evaluation and a qualitative internal assessment by the Ministry of Education (conducted in Arabic as of 2015). It was designed by the author of this study under the guidance of a team of Arabic language teachers and includes a vowelized section in Arabic (called "Green Gas") (all the questions taken from the "Meitzav" test). In Arabic, the text is called "Bio Diesel". It was selected from a series of national tests for measuring and mapping achievements ("Meitzav", 2015) according to the new curriculum (2012). The test is designed to examine different levels of understanding ideas at a local and global level, as well as implementation and conclusion. The examinees were required to read the text and answer 13 multiple-choice questions, while the number of correct answers is specified.
8. Reading assessment tests (Asadi, 2012). In the first stage, a test was conducted according to the division of study population (junior high school and high school) to evaluate reading and ensure that the reading ability of the students with reading disabilities was indeed significantly lower than that of the regular readers.
9. Reading accuracy test for middle school (Alpha = 0.88). The test was written by the author of this study under the guidance of a team of Arabic language teachers, and includes 50 vowelized words that are graded from easy to difficult. The easy words consist of 2-3 letters or 1-2 syllables. The difficult words have more syllables, consisting of four letters or more, and are usually vowelized with a sign, which duplicates the letter. The words were taken from Arabic textbooks approved by the Ministry of Education for junior high schools. The test was administered individually in a quiet room at the school. Each student read aloud the

list of words, and the examiner noted the number of words that were read correctly, as well as the number of words that were read incorrectly.

10. Reading accuracy test for high school students ($\text{Alpha} = 0.88$). The test was written by the author of this study under the guidance of a team of the Arabic language teachers and includes 50 vowelized words graded from easy to difficult. The easy words consist of 2-3 letters or 1-2 syllables. The difficult words have more syllables, consisting of four letters or more, and are usually vowelized with a sign, which duplicates the letter. The words were taken from Arabic textbooks by the Ministry of Education for high schools. The test was administered individually in a quiet room at the school. Each student read aloud the list of words, and the examiner noted the number of words that were read correctly, as well as the number of words that were read incorrectly.

Results

In order to examine the first hypothesis of the study, a multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted. It examined the effect of reading disability on social competence, self-image and academic achievement levels using the Hotelling's trace criterion. The general multivariate effect was found to be significant [$F_{(8,372)} = 5.68, p < 0.001$]. As can be seen in Table 1, significant differences were found in each of the dependent variables, as stated in the hypothesis. It can be deduced that the hypothesis has been fully confirmed.

Table 1: Social competence, self-image and academic achievements of RD adolescents (boys and girls) and normal adolescents

Dependent variables	Students with RD (N=206)	Normal (N=175)	Students F _(1,379)	Eta ²
General social competence	3.01 (0.59)	3.71 (0.53)	144.904***	0.28
Social competence-cooperation scale	2.96 (0.75)	3.73 (0.66)	110.164***	0.23
Social competence-Assertiveness scale	3.02 (0.68)	3.68 (0.61)	97.024***	0.2
Social competence-Empathy scale	3.12 (0.65)	3.80 (0.57)	116.35***	0.23
Social competence-Self-control scale	2.90 (0.67)	3.58 (0.79)	83.531***	0.18
Self-image	3.42 (0.54)	4.32 (0.53)	264.574***	0.41
Reading comprehension	4.93 (2.14)	10.53 (1.91)	715.285***	0.65
Reading accuracy	19.94 (8.92)	47.49 (2.96)	1525.625***	0.8

*** $p < 0.001$

To examine the second hypothesis, the relationship between the degrees of socio-emotional support at home and at school was reviewed in conjunction with the reading comprehension and accuracy scores among students with reading disabilities and normal students, separately. The results of the hypothesis are presented in Table 2 below, and it appears that according to the hypothesis, there is a positive correlation between socio-emotional support indicators and academic achievements among adolescent students with reading disabilities only, and therefore the hypothesis was confirmed.

Table 2: Pearson's correlation coefficients between social emotional support and academic achievements among students with disabilities and normal students

Socio-emotional support	Students with reading disability (N=206)		Normal students (N=175)	
	Reading comprehension	Reading accuracy	Reading comprehension	Reading accuracy
Socio-emotional Support at school	.26***	.34***	-.01	-.08
Socio-emotional Support at home	.20**	.25***	-.01	-.15

* $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$

To examine the third hypothesis, a multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the combined effect of disability and socio-emotional support on social competence, self-image and achievements in reading comprehension and reading accuracy, using the Hotelling's trace criterion. Statistical analysis allowed to detect a significant general multivariate effect of disability [$F_{(8,370)} = 248.00, p < 0.001, \text{Eta}^2 = 0.843$], and a significant general multivariate effect of emotional support [$F_{(8,370)} = 5.43, p < 0.001, \text{Eta}^2 = 0.11$]. In

addition, a significant general multivariate interaction effect was detected [$F^{(8,370)} = 3.33, p < 0.01, \eta^2 = 0.07$]. The source of disability effect stems from all the reviewed indicators, except for the reading comprehension achievements (see Table 3). The source of the interaction stems from the scales of social competence, cooperation and self-control, as well as from reading comprehension and reading accuracy scores (see Figures 1-4). The interaction pattern in each of the effects indicates a significant difference between students with reading disability who received socio-emotional support and those who did not. Therefore, socio-emotional support increases the indicators, but among the normal students, there was no significant difference between those who received socio-emotional support and those who did not.

Table 3: Differences between adolescents (boys and girls) who received emotional support and adolescents who did not receive emotional support regarding social competence, self-image and academic achievements

Dependent variables	Students with socio-emotional support (N=253)	Students without socio-emotional support (N=128)	$F_{(1,377)}$	η^2
General social competence	3.5 (0.56)	3.00 (0.71)	32.2***	0.08
Social competence - Cooperation scale	3.51 (0.69)	2.93 (0.89)	28.22***	0.07
Social competence - Assertiveness scale	3.48 (0.67)	3.01 (0.73)	23.60***	0.06
Social competence - Empathy scale	3.58 (0.61)	3.14 (0.77)	19.88***	0.05
Social competence - Self-control scale	3.36 (0.77)	2.91 (0.78)	13.98***	0.04
Self-image	3.99 (0.63)	3.53 (0.72)	23.05***	0.06
Reading comprehension	8.00 (3.26)	6.52 (3.62)	1.59	0.004
Reading accuracy	35.49 (13.90)	26.87 (16.51)	12.55***	0.03

*** $p < .001$

Fig. 1: Combined effect of disability and emotional support on social competence and cooperation scale

Fig. 2: Combined effect of disability and emotional support on social competence and self-control scale

Fig. 3: Combined effect of disability and emotional support on reading comprehension

Fig. 4: Combined effect of disability and emotional support on reading accuracy

Discussion

Hypothesis 1

The first hypothesis assumes that a group of students with RD (male & female) will report a lower level of social competence, self-image and academic achievements than a group of normal students. The findings of the study fully confirmed this hypothesis.

Literature reports an existence of mutual effect between reading RD and socio-emotional factors. Social competence has been defined as the ability to use personal and environmental resources to achieve personal or mutual benefit in various walks of life. Social competence enables the attainment of personal goals via socially acceptable interactions (Sroufe & Waters, 1983). This indicates that a person's social performance is conducted in accordance with the accepted practice. Social competence is not an innate character trait, but rather includes behaviors acquired over the years that affect the relationship of an individual with his peer group. It includes three areas of functioning: behavioral, emotional and cognitive, which focus on thinking and learning processes, as well as on the way by which the individual perceives and interprets reality (La Greca, 1988; Margalit, 2014).

In current study, the first hypothesis examined social competence as a social aspect and was divided into four factors: cooperation, assertiveness, self-control and empathy. The findings showed that the level of social competence among Arab adolescent boys and girls with RD is lower than that of normal Arab adolescent boys and girls. These findings corroborate and correspond with findings of many researchers who claim that RD have a direct link to social deficits and impairments in children and adults with disabilities (Margalit, 2014; Tarabeh, 2015; Yagil, 2006).

Poor social competence is explained as a defect in cognitive processes and difficulty to process and understand social knowledge effectively via interpersonal communication, and emotional difficulties, which cause the child to have difficulty to interpret social events effectively and correctly, focus attention to significant social clues, understand social situations, draw conclusion for problem solutions, analyze wrong information from the environment and understand others (Bryan, 1991; Margalit, 2013). Poor social competence among children with RD reduces their chances to form healthy social relationships and function efficiently, leading to emotional difficulties. Thus, those children are seen as being frustrated, lacking motivation, unstable, rebellious, anxious, depressive and aggressive with low self-esteem, low self-confidence and lonely. (Gresham & Reschly, 1989). Low social competence among students with RD, especially with reading disability, impairs their capacity to establish interpersonal relationships with their peers, leading to emotional implications, which are expressed in a sense of loneliness and low self-esteem (Sima et al., 2016).

In addition to social competence, the current study examined the self-image among Arab RD adolescent girls and boys. We assumed to find that the self-image among Arab adolescent girls and boys with RDs is lower than that of normal Arab adolescent girls and boys. The findings of this study fully confirm this assumption. The development of self-perception and self-image among children with reading disability is complex because it is

affected by low academic performance at school, alongside the socio-emotional difficulties (Azaiza & Ben-Ari, 1998). James defined self-image as an index of failures and successes (James, 1890): the index rises if one's aspirations are fulfilled and he/she then receives a positive social appraisal that elevates the self-image, and it descends in the wake of failures when the individual asks "Who am I?", and receives a reply to this question through the evaluation of those around him, of his property, his actions and his achievements (Lackaye et al., 2006).

In addition, it was found that the capacities and educational achievements of boys and girls with RD are poor. In recent years, comparative data on reading achievement tests and reading comprehension among students in the Arab society in Israel has been published. It indicates that the Arab students' achievements are lower than those of students who speak other languages, mostly in comparison to Hebrew speakers (Margalit, 2014). One of the reasons for this phenomenon is related to diglossia that characterizes the Arabic language. It is expressed by the gap between the spoken and written language, spanning such aspects as sentence structure, language components, reading, phonology, morphology, syntax and vocabulary (Ibrahim, Eviatar & Peretz, 2007; Ibrahim, 2006; Jones & Burden, 2009).

A study that examined the reading pace of students with RD and speed difficulties (Denckla et al., 2013), indicates a slow pace of information processing, which impairs the efficiency of performing roles that require simultaneous processing of several stimuli. They indeed acquire normal reading skills, but may have difficulty in reading comprehension, and their management function is not suitable for coping with the text correctly and effectively. The findings of Denckla and his colleagues are well supported by the results of our study, and explain why male and female students with RD have low scores on both reading accuracy and reading comprehension tests (Denckla et al., 2013).

Hypothesis 2

The second research hypothesis was that socio-emotional support would be a variable that would mediate between the disability and academic achievements. Specifically, it was assumed that among students with reading disabilities, there would be a positive correlation between socio-emotional support and academic achievements, while among normal students there is no such correlation. Indeed, the findings of this study show that students with reading disabilities have a significantly positive correlation between receiving socio-emotional support and academic achievements, while among normal students there is no such correlation. In other words, the disability (reading disability/normal) provides the link between socio-emotional support and positive academic achievements. Students with reading disabilities have that link, while high socio-emotional support contributes to academic success, and if the students are normal, there is no link between socio-emotional support and academic success. Therefore, it appears that this hypothesis has been fully confirmed. In research literature, it has been reported that support provided to others (Han, 2014; Shirey, 2004; Suzan & Aytac, 2017) can be tangible or intangible, and protection includes shielding and protecting others from the negative effects of life pressures.

Socio-emotional support is the most important one (Thoits, 1985; Zhang et al., 2015); social rejection or acceptance affects emotional wellbeing, since socio-emotional support increases emotional wellbeing and has a positive impact on the recipient's learning development. These findings can be supported by the findings of a study that compared people with social acceptance and positive social feedback to people who feel lonely due to negative social feedback (Buckley, Winkel & Leary, 2004), and it was found to be due to lack of empowerment and socio-emotional support. When it comes to support, it should also be noted that working with students who have learning disabilities involves interaction and cooperation between three systems - child, educational system and family. The latter two are entities that provide socio-emotional support to the child and are relevant to his/her empowerment and success. The value of parental participation is in planning the educational process, especially when it comes to parenting children with learning disabilities, which is unique, complex and fraught with difficulties (Ziv, 2014; Plotnik, 2008; Atalay, 2013). Therefore, most intervention programs concerning students with learning disabilities focused on cognitive improvement and learning skills. Only recently, an emphasis has been put on the importance of emotion and motivation. Therefore, the socio-emotional support received by an adolescent with learning disabilities in general and reading disabilities in particular is important for improving his/her emotional wellbeing, academic performance and achievements, since students who perceive themselves as not benefiting from socio-emotional support, express negative attitudes toward the learning environment and are perceived as having low academic self-image and achievements (Conroy, & Elliot, 2004; Saada, 2007; Suzan & Aytac, 2017).

Hypothesis 3

The third hypothesis was that students who receive socio-emotional support would report higher socio-emotional indicators, and would demonstrate higher academic achievements than those who do not receive emotional support. In addition, there would be a combined effect between disabilities and emotional support, so that students with reading disabilities who receive socio-emotional support will still report lower socio-emotional indicators and academic achievements than normal students.

In current study, it was consistently found that achievements of adolescents with reading disabilities are low compared to normal adolescents. Moreover, the second hypothesis revealed an effect of socio-emotional support by contributing to academic achievements, especially in the field of reading comprehension. Further to the sequence of these findings, a combined effect was found in each of the indicators between disability and socio-emotional support among students with reading disability. The third hypothesis that reviewed social competence in general and on the scales of social competence, cooperation and self-control in particular, as well as the achievements in reading comprehension and accuracy, also detected this effect. Therefore, among adolescents with reading disabilities, those who received socio-emotional support reported social competence, collaboration and self-control, as well as higher level of reading comprehension and accuracy than those who did not receive socio-emotional support. Such difference between the two groups (those who received socio-emotional support and those who did not) does not exist among the normal student. In other words, socio-emotional support is more significant for adolescents with reading disabilities, since this type of support contributes to the improvement of socio-emotional and academic indicators.

Furthermore, the hypothesis that in each of the indicators it would be found that students with reading disabilities who receive social emotional support would still report lower socio-emotional indicators and academic achievements than normal students has been fully confirmed. These findings can be supported by research literature. Due to repeated cognitive failures, adolescents with learning disabilities tend to develop symptoms of emotional stress: low self-esteem, lack of social competence and a sense of loneliness. In order to adapt to the social system, as well as acquire social competence that provides high self-esteem and sense of belonging that reduces the feeling of loneliness, efficient utilization of reading skills is required (Lamm & Epstein, 1994). Children with learning disabilities lack such skills, in addition to lack of socio-emotional that is considered meaningful to their emotional wellbeing and adaptation (Suzan & Aytac, 2017).

The links between the social environment of adolescent students and motivation to study are maintained even when examined in context of ethnic minority. It was found that any positive feedback from adults that is considered socio-emotional support for adolescents belonging to minority groups contributes significantly to self-image and has an impact on social aspects (Suzan & Aytac, 2017; Saada, 2007). Adolescent students are familiar with a wide range of purposes related to school activities. Therefore, social environment is an extremely important developmental factor that supports, encourages and stimulates learning through self-guidance and motivation to learn. This guidance emphasizes the need for social and classroom interactions that have a positive impact on the student's self-image and achievement orientation. In addition, the climate in the classroom must be emphasized as a psychological environment that provides and fosters emotion (Deci, Ryan & Williams, 1996; Suzan & Aytac, 2017). In addition, classroom climate is considered a type of socio-educational support that has a great impact on adolescents and their attitude, mood, emotional wellbeing, educational behavior and self-perception (Reeve & Jang, 2006). Moreover, studies (Assor, Kaplan & Roth, 2002) show that students who feel the support of their teachers regarding their autonomy and ability to conduct their studies adequately (Ziv, 2014; Saada, 2007; Suzan & Aytac, 2017; Sandy, Kgoale & Mavundla, 2013).

Summary and conclusions

Due to all of the above, it can be emphasized that socio-emotional support has a unique contribution to the social emotional aspect, whether to social competence and social interaction in the environment of the disabled, or to the learning environment of the adolescent who receives support from a teacher or parent, or the broad school system that increases expectations for success. This emphasizes the rationale of the article, which raises the significance of socio-emotional support as a factor influencing the emotional wellbeing and academic aspect that supports the statement that if I am not free emotionally – I am not free from academic point of view (Tarabia & Abu-Rabia, 2016).

The significance of social support can be summarized via the main results we have obtained in this study:

1. It was found that on the scales of social competence, cooperation and self-control, as well as in reading comprehension and accuracy scores, a combined effect was detected between reading disability socio-emotional support. In each of the indicators, it was found that among all adolescents with reading disability, those who received emotional support reported a higher level of social competence, cooperation, self-control, reading comprehension and accuracy than students who did not receive socio-emotional support. Normal students did not demonstrate any difference between those who received social support and those who did not receive emotional support. In other words, socio-emotional support among adolescents with reading disabilities improves emotional, social and learning variables, however, the indicators are still lower than in normal adolescents in all of the above.
2. A positive correlation was detected between socio-emotional support and social competence, self-image and academic achievements.

Furthermore, it was found the scale of assertiveness in social competence has a unique contribution to predicting achievements in reading comprehension among adolescent boys and girls with reading disabilities.

It can be concluded that socio-emotional support mediates between social competence and reading accuracy, and improves social and emotional indicators, as well as the achievements of adolescent boys and girls with reading disabilities.

In order to reduce these difficulties, the educational system must seek and provide relevant solutions that will advance the proper development of these students. The concept of treating students with learning disabilities that is currently being established, suggests that the treatment should be integrated and multidisciplinary. A complete therapeutic program should include socio-emotional support, while treating the child as an individual and the family as a system, in addition to the cultural, educational and socio-emotional environment.

Socio-emotional support increases the chances of students with learning disabilities, especially when it comes to students of various ages from the Arab sector (junior high school and high school), to integrate into society and develop properly. The support of parents and school during adolescence is considered a factor promoting adaptation and educational skills (Lewis, Amatya, Coffman & Olendick, 2015). Moreover, healthy relationships during adolescence can protect adolescents with emotional problems acquire as a result of stressful life events, since healthy support and relationship are characterized by a balance between autonomy and closeness, which helps the adolescent develop emotional resilience (Laursen & Collins, 2013).

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